

The Legacy Mosaic Data Rescue Project

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In the mid-1990s, telescopes at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) and Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) made the significant transition to archiving digital observational data. At that time, desktop computers could store about 1 Gigabyte, or about 1000 times less than what a modern smartphone can now store. To meet the storage needs of data-intensive astronomy at that time, magnetic tape was the most cost-effective medium.

The National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO; National Optical Astronomy Observatories pre-FY2000) collected 5+ million raw data files on 9000+ unique data magnetic tapes from 1993 until 2004. Principal Investigators (PIs) received a tape copy of their program data, but at the time there was no searchable archive of all observations. By 2004, modern disk storage technology facilitated digital archives. From that point forward, nightly observations and reductions were stored in the NOAO Science Archive, which became the NOIRLab Astro Data Archive in 2019.

Fast forward to today, and 9000 8mm tape cartridges remain housed in the NOIRLab Tucson Headquarters data center. A mirror collection of the same tapes is stored on Kitt Peak.

These tapes were retained after being written at the telescope but were seldom accessed thereafter. The 8mm tape format, which is similar to what video cameras of the same generation used for recording, is obsolete. Each tape can store about 7 Gigabytes, or less than a thumb drive by today's standards. The tape data have been offline for the past 20–30 years despite numerous possibilities for archival research. The Mayall 4m Mosaic-1 data are similar to modern Mosaic-3 data, facilitating direct comparison of object changes over time (Figure 1).

These legacy data also have historical significance. According to Tod Lauer, *“The tape archive contains the original images used by two separate teams to discover the effects of ‘dark-energy’ on the expansion of the Universe (in short, by discovering supernovae that were used as ‘standard candles’ to assess distances to galaxies over extremely large scales). These observations revolutionized modern cosmology and were recognized with three Nobel prizes in physics in 2011.”*

There has always been interest in recovering the data on the tapes, but there were never resources available or sufficient motivation to do the actual work. Eventually, the data will not be recoverable because the tapes will degrade and the hardware to recover them will no longer be available. The time is now to recover the tapes while current institutional knowledge can assist in processing and cataloging the data properly.

Using a bank of 20 8mm tape readers, the recovery project team (Randy Faux, Nick Foo, Sean McManus) has managed to extract 50% of the data from the tapes, so far, including nearly all Mosaic-1 wide-field-imager data. The raw files are currently being characterized and prepared for Astro Data Archive ingest. Frank

Figure 1: Exabyte tape drives for the Astro Data Legacy Tape Drive Archive.
Credit: R. Faux/NOIRLab

Valdes will adapt existing pipeline software to perform basic calibration to produce science-ready images. According to Valdes, “*Our ability to calibrate these data, both in terms of quality and computational speed, has advanced, and so the archived calibrated images produced from these imagers will be state-of-the-art.*”

The American Astronomical Society (AAS) is collaborating with NOIRLab on this project. They have created an AAS Archive Fellowship for a quarter-time graduate student to work on both the Abt Archives and the Data Rescue Project. The Abt Archives is a physical collection of peer review records of approximately 35,000 manuscript files related to *The Astrophysical Journal* (ApJ) during the editorship of Helmut A. Abt (NOAO, ret.), who served from 1971 through 1999 using a manual, paper-intensive review process. The AAS Archive Fellow is logging these records into a database and repacking them into archival storage materials for preservation (Figure 2).

Figure 2: (left) Peer review files in the Abt Archives stored in archival boxes after processing; (right) files before logging and repacking. Credit: J. Steffen/AAS

These two archival projects are preserving important aspects of our astronomical heritage by conserving, organizing, and making accessible these two archival collections.

This image of the Andromeda Galaxy (M31) was created with data from the Local Group Survey, completed with the Mosaic camera on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory. Ten 'pointings' of the camera along the galaxy in five filters were used to make the image. About 600 million pixels in size, it is the largest and most detailed image of M31 ever completed that covers the entire galaxy. The image release can be found [here](#).

Credit: Local Group Survey Team and T.A. Rector (University of Alaska Anchorage)